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Abstract	This deliverable builds upon D5.1 and outlines progress in applying Artificial Intelligence and High-Performance Computing within the AD4GD project. It details the use of AI models in pilot studies, such as water level prediction in Berlin lakes and connectivity mapping in Catalonia, highlighting the AI models ability to process complex environmental data efficiently. The document also presents the development of user-friendly interfaces that make these advanced tools accessible to non-expert stakeholders, promoting informed decision-making. Additionally, it reports on the integration of HPC resources to support AI model training and execution, enhancing performance and scalability. The deliverable concludes with reflections on the benefits, limitations, and future directions of these technologies in AD4GD pilots.
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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
ARIMA	AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average
c-GAN	conditional Generative Adversarial Network
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FLC	Functional Landscape Connectivity
FROST	Fraunhofer Opensource SensorThings-Server
GDDS	Green Deal Data Space
HCD	Human-Centred Design
HPC	High-Performance Computing
ICT	Integral terrestrial connectivity index
IoT	Internet of Things
LSTM	Long short-term memory
LULC	Land-use land-cover
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
MSE	Mean Squared Error
MUCSC	Map of Uses and Covers of Catalonia
ReLU	Rectified Linear activation Unit
REST	Representational State Transfer
RNN	Recurrent Neural network
SARIMA	Seasonal AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average
SSIM	Structural Similarity Index Measure
STA	SensorThings API
STApplus	SensorThings API plus
UI	User Interface

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable D5.2 “Artificial Intelligence resources for Earth system modelling” is the natural continuation of D5.1 and summarises the progress during the second half of AD4GD project on Artificial Intelligence (AI) and High Performance Computing (HPC) usage for assisting pilot studies, the design and implementation of User Interfaces (UIs), and the integration of such tools with those coming from the other Work Packages (WPs) of AD4GD.

As established in D5.1, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a powerful tool for addressing environmental challenges such as those posed by AD4GD pilots. Its potential to analyse vast datasets and identify complex patterns makes AI models great candidates to substitute computationally complex and time-consuming tasks, enabling or accelerating the process of extracting useful insights from large amounts of data. The first part of this document gets into the details of the results of applying AI models to cases such as pilot 1 for predicting water level for lakes in Berlin area, and the possible impact of rains on them, or to help providing fast calculation of connectivity maps in the Catalonia region for pilot 2. The advantages and disadvantages of these methods are discussed in depth, and some future lines to be potentially pursued after the closing of AD4GD are also proposed.

Since this is the last deliverable of WP5, another part of the document deals with presenting the work done in the context of this project to develop a user-friendly and intuitive interface, which is crucial for effective decision-making in the context of the pilots mentioned above. This interface allows stakeholders and general users, often non-experts in environmental science or technology, easily accessing and understanding complex data and models. By providing clear visualizations, interactive tools, and intuitive navigation, a well-designed UI empowers decision-makers to quickly identify trends, assess risks, and explore potential solutions. This accessibility fosters a more informed and engaged stakeholders, ultimately leading to better-informed policy decisions and more effective environmental management strategies.

Finally, this document reports on the usage of HPC resources to cope with the computational demands of AI applications. HPC clusters enable AI models to be trained on massive datasets, improving their accuracy and efficiency in solving problems as the one described. In addition, HPC can accelerate AI-driven simulations and predictions, allowing for more timely and informed decision-making.

1 INTRODUCTION

This document (Deliverable 5.2 of the AD4GD project) presents the final results achieved in the context of Tasks 5.1 “AI and ML for data quality and uncertainty management and ground-truthing”, 5.2 “AI, ML in HPC and cloud for data analytics and knowledge generation”, 5.3 “User interface definition for intuitive decision making”, 5.4 “Front-end implementation of AD4GD user applications” and 5.5 “Supporting convergence of High Performance Computing, cloud, data and artificial intelligence resources for Earth system modelling” as part of Work Package 5 “Artificial Intelligence for Data Certainty, Quality and Exploitability”. This deliverable is the last instalment of WP5 deliverables and builds upon the contents presented in D5.1. For that reason, D5.1 will be referenced several times in this document, and some contents may be reused for improving readability and making the deliverable as self-contained as possible.

The work developed in WP5 is divided into three main blocks:

- Development, deployment and validation of AI models for AD4GD pilots: Section 2 of this document delves deep into the details of the AI models developed to cope with the requirements coming from pilots 1 and 2 of AD4GD, detailing the process of selecting and training the AI model, the rationale behind the choices, the data available and how it has impacted the design and implementation process, the pipeline creation and deployment into the HPC resources of the project, and the final validation performed together with the involved stakeholders, considering both functional and non-functional requirements.
- Design, development and implementation of user interfaces: A Human-Centred Design (HCD) approach was employed to develop user interfaces focusing on an iterative design to foster stakeholder collaboration. Section 3 details the design and implementation work for two pilot tools: SplashBoard and BioConnect, focussing on the implemented functionalities based on user requirements gathered through the HCD approach. SplashBoard features data visualization, interactive lake statistics and AI-driven water level predictions; while BioConnect allows users to simulate land usage changes and analyse ecological impacts via AI-driven connectivity index calculations. Additionally, a prototype for the Green Deal General User Interface was developed as a best practice example. The implementation of both pilot tools utilized the open. DASH¹ platform for modular design, with a final tool evaluation planned to ensure alignment with user requirements in D6.2.
- Integration of data, AI, edge and HPC resources to provide end-to-end pipelines for the pilots developed in AD4GD: Section 4 provides an updated version of how the different components of AD4GD (data, AI, HPC, edge and cloud) were finally orchestrated and integrated, describing how the pipelines of the pilots are deployed and where the different modules are executed. One of the main updates was the finalisation of the data harmonization tool from WP1 and its deployment in the HPC resources of the project.

Finally, the document closes with reflections on the benefits, limitations, and future directions of these technologies in AD4GD pilots.

¹ <https://open-dash.com/>

2 MACHINE LEARNING FOR DATA ANALYTICS AND KNOWLEDGE GENERATION

In D5.1, the first steps towards the development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) /Machine Learning (ML) models for pilot 1 and pilot 2 were described. To ease the reading of this document, the following subsections will start with a brief summary of the content reported in the previous deliverable, and then the deliverable will delve deeper into the details of the new developments since D5.1 was delivered. Consequently, some contents (e.g., figures) can be repeated from D5.1, but it will be clearly indicated throughout the text.

2.1 PILOT 1: WATER AVAILABILITY/QUALITY

As described in D5.1, Pilot 1 is built around the idea of using AI/ML to prioritize conservation efforts and identify drought potential in lakes. To develop this idea, the city of Berlin was chosen: its more than 300 small urban lakes offer valuable biodiversity and recreational opportunities, but they suffer from summer high temperatures and droughts and have to deal with the pressure from urbanization and climate change. As a result, water availability is a major issue for Berlin lakes, which endangers the vital ecosystems they nurture. Subsequently, this puts at risk the many benefits the lake system brings to the city of Berlin: lakes serve as the habitat of diverse aquatic life or contributing to mitigating the effects of climate change by regulating local temperatures and absorbing rainwater, which in turn helps in preventing flooding. As a result, understanding water availability trends is vital to maintain the quality of life of Berlin's population.

2.1.1 MODELS DEVELOPMENT, DEPLOYMENT AND VALIDATION

In order to enable Berlin's authorities to make data-driven decisions regarding water conservation and management in its urban lakes, WP5 objective is to use AI/ML models to predict the water availability for lakes in Berlin area, particularly focusing on how different precipitation conditions might affect lake water levels. As described in D5.1, the approach proposed for pilot 1 was to use the available historical data of both water level and weather data (such as precipitations) to train a model to predict the future behaviour of lakes. To achieve this goal, data was gathered from two different sources: the water level was obtained from Wasserportal Berlin², where other relevant variables such as ground water level could be found as well, while weather data was collected from Open-Meteo³. With these preliminary datasets selected, the next step of the process was to choose the most suitable model for obtaining these predictions. With the data being historical values of water level and precipitation over time, the AI/ML problem to be solved was a time series forecasting problem. In this scenario, several model candidates were evaluated, namely three: ARIMA (AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average), SARIMA (Seasonal ARIMA), and LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory). In a nutshell:

- **ARIMA [1], [2], [3]:** It is one of the most widely used models for time series forecasting due to its simplicity and broad applicability, which was the reason why it was originally chosen. However, despite its historical success and widespread popularity, ARIMA presented some inherent limitations: 1) the model assumes that the statistical properties of the data, such as mean and variance, remain constant over time, which makes it not suitable for scenarios dealing with data that exhibits complex seasonal or trend-based behaviours; 2) ARIMA struggles to model long-term dependencies or non-linear relationships, which are commonly found in environmental data, especially with irregular patterns caused by external factors like weather or climate change. As a result, the model had difficulty handling the seasonal variations in water levels and precipitation.

² <https://wasserportal.berlin.de/>

³ <https://open-meteo.com/>

- **SARIMA [1], [3]:** It is an extension of ARIMA that includes seasonal components to the model with the objective of overcoming the challenge of seasonality introduced before. This modification is particularly useful when the data exhibits seasonal trends, which is common in environmental data, which often vary according to different seasons. Although SARIMA is more powerful than ARIMA for dealing with seasonal data, it still faced limitations in pilot 1 specific case. The seasonality patterns in the water level data were complex and unpredictable, often influenced by various external factors such as sudden weather changes or urban activities in combination with urban catchment characteristics, which could not be easily captured by the model. As a result, the complexity and variability of the seasonal patterns in the data highlighted the need for a more flexible and adaptive model.
- **LSTM [4], [5]:** Considering the challenges of ARIMA and SARIMA in capturing complex, non-linear, and long-term dependencies in the data, a more advanced and flexible model was selected: LSTM networks. LSTM networks are a type of Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) designed specifically for learning from sequences of data. They are well-suited for handling long-term dependencies in data, which makes them particularly effective for forecasting tasks involving time-series data that exhibit complex patterns. LSTMs are capable of learning and remembering information for extended periods, making them much more robust when dealing with real-world data that includes non-linear relationships and complex temporal dependencies.

To sum up, the decision of choosing LSTM over ARIMA and SARIMA, was based on the following:

- Ability to capture long-term dependencies, which is crucial in forecasting of environmental variables where the behaviour of the system at one point can have long-lasting effects, as observed in the persistence of water level changes over time.
- Handling non-linearity, since this is essential when forecasting environmental data, as the relationship between precipitation and water levels is often non-linear.
- Adaptability to changing patterns, which is desirable when dealing with data influenced by rapidly changing environmental conditions like climate change or urbanization.
- Improved forecasting performance, especially when having large datasets with complex dependencies, as is the case of pilot 1.

As mentioned at the beginning of this section, the data used to train the LSTM reported in D5.1 were time-series datasets prepared from the historical data extracted from Wasserportal Berlin and Open-Meteo. However, when validating these results, it was seen that the meteorological data used was too generic: for all the lakes being forecasted, the weather information of the whole Berlin area was being used instead of the weather of the specific region where each lake was located. The specific local information was used to refine the input dataset and, subsequently, the model itself, tailoring it to each specific lake. Figure 2.1 details the final model architecture for the LSTM, which contains the following layers:

- **Input layer:** It expects a sequence of data with a shape (None, seq_size), where None indicates an arbitrary sequence length, and seq_size corresponds to the number of features (e.g., water level, precipitation, etc.) in the input at each timestep.
- **First LSTM layer:** It consists of 128 units and uses the rectified linear activation unit (ReLU) activation function, which is commonly used in the literature and introduces non-linearity to the model, allowing the model to learn complex patterns in the data by activating only positive values and ensuring that the model learns to differentiate between important and less important features [6], [7]. This first layer outputs the full sequence to the next layer rather than only the last timestep. This is crucial when stacking multiple LSTM layers, as it allows the model to preserve temporal dependencies throughout the sequence.

- **Second LSTM layer:** It consists of 64 units, with the ReLU activation function applied again. The output from the first LSTM layer is passed to this second layer, which helps the model to further refine its learning and capture more complex dependencies.
- **First dense layer:** It has 64 units and serves as a fully connected layer to combine the features learned by the LSTM layers.
- **Second dense layer:** It has a single unit, which outputs the predicted water level for the lake at the next timestep.

Figure 2.1 Detail on the architecture of the final LSTM model developed for pilot 1

From an implementation point of view, the model uses Mean Squared Error (MSE) as the loss function. MSE helps penalize large errors more than small ones, which is crucial when predicting water levels where significant discrepancies in predictions could have serious consequences. Regarding the optimization of the model, Adam (Adaptive Moment Estimation) is used as optimizer. Adam is a highly effective optimizer that requires little memory and is particularly well-suited for problems with large datasets and noisy gradients, making it a great choice for environmental forecasting tasks [8]. Additionally, key callbacks are used to improve training: model checkpoint, which saves the model at its best state during training, ensuring that the final model is the one that performed best on the validation data; and early stopping, which stops the training when the model's performance on the validation set stops improving, preventing overfitting and ensuring efficient use of computational resources.

Once trained, the model is capable of recursive forecasting, meaning it can generate predictions for future water levels step-by-step, using its own predictions as inputs for subsequent time steps. To effectively combine the water level and weather data, three different forecasting scenarios were defined:

- **Forecasting based on predicted precipitation:** The model predicts future water levels using expected future precipitation data.
- **Zero precipitation forecast:** The model predicts water levels assuming no future precipitation (a worst-case scenario, simulating a drought period).
- **Fixed high precipitation forecast:** The model predicts water levels assuming a constant, high level of precipitation, simulating extreme weather conditions (which is something likely to happen due to climate change impact on weather). This high precipitation threshold was specifically tailored for each lake, searching for the maximum value recorded in the historical data for each lake and

defining it as a 75% of this value. This threshold was selected after conducting empirical experiments with various precipitation values, with this specific value providing the best results in terms of model performance during testing.

The results obtained with this LSTM are going to be deeply analysed in Section 2.1.3. As a future line of improvement after AD4GD, the experiment of combining the forecasted values with the clustering technique tested in D5.1 is still a research opportunity to explore. As established in D5.1, the ultimate goal was to get a clustered classification of the lakes based on their behaviour considering both historical, current and predicted values. However, the process of identifying the variables in the available data that contribute to that output is still a work in progress and spans of out the scope of AD4GD.

2.1.2 AI MODELS' PIPELINES

As reported in D5.1, Pilot 1 implementation in WP5 provides an AI prediction model pipeline that has a configurable pre-scheduled run. The model was trained according to the ML lifecycle defined in D5.1, and which is repeated here in Figure 2.2 for readability purposes.

Figure 2.2: AD4GD MLOps – ML model lifecycle implementation (extracted from D5.1)

As can be observed, the fourth step in the ML lifecycle is model inference, which represents the behaviour of the model once it is put in production for its use in making predictions. This process can be observed in Figure 2.3, which also comes from D5.1. The AI model pipeline was already configured when the previous deliverable was submitted, which is why no changes are required in the image.

The AI prediction pipeline for pilot 1 works as follows:

- First, the incoming raw data is stored in MinIO, an object storage system which is hosted in the context of the AD4GD project on the HPC cluster deployed in the PSNC premises. MinIO provides an API fully compatible with the Amazon S3 cloud storage system
- When this action is performed, an MQTT notification is automatically generated to launch the data harmonization tool coming from WPI. This process is further described in Section 4.2 of this document.
- This tool produces the harmonized data, which are also stored in MinIO.
- Once the new harmonized data is available, it is ingested to the model, which was deployed through Kserve⁴, an open-source Kubernetes-based tool for serving ML models at scale.
- The predicted values generated by the model are also stored in MinIO.
- These values can then be further used/consumed by any interested stakeholder.

At the moment of writing this deliverable, this process is run in a weekly basis, which is the frequency with which new data from Pilot 1 is made available in MinIO.

⁴ <https://kserve.github.io/website/latest/>

Figure 2.3: Pilot 1 ML Model's inferencing schema (extracted from D5.1)

2.1.3 RESULTS

As established in D5.1, the work reported there in the context of pilot 1 was limited to presenting a first version of the LSTM model and some preliminary results obtained for one of the lakes. The rationale behind having the results for just one lake was that, up until that moment, harmonized data coming from WP1 was not available yet, and it was crucial for setting up the AI/ML pipeline, as shown in Figure 2.3, since it would simplify the pre-processing step needed to develop ML models. Without the harmonized data, the models should be manually retrained, so it was decided to wait for the harmonized data to train them, and the efforts were put on completing the pipeline described before to automate the whole process. In this deliverable, the results for all lakes are reported, with all developments successfully completed, including the data harmonization tool coming from WP1.

The LSTM model expects the past 180 days of data as input to predict the water level for the following 7 days. To provide a detailed performance evaluation, Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean Squared Error (MSE) were calculated for each scenario across all lakes using the validation data. These results are summarized in Table 2.1. As previously mentioned in Section 2.1.1, the prediction process considers three different scenarios to account for sudden variations in precipitation that deviate from the normal tendency. Consequently, Table 2.1 contains the following information:

- The *High precipitation* columns indicate the error obtained when high precipitations are assumed, simulating a persistently rainy week.
- The *Forecast* columns correspond to predictions generated using real future precipitation forecasts.
- The *Zero precipitation* columns represent the case where future precipitation is set to zero.

Each scenario is evaluated using both MAE and MSE:

- MAE measures the average absolute difference between the predicted and actual water levels, providing a direct interpretation of average error in units of water level.
- MSE, which squares the error before averaging, penalizes larger deviations more heavily and is therefore more sensitive to outliers.

The results show that the forecast scenario consistently achieves lower MAE and MSE values compared to the other two scenarios across nearly all lakes, indicating that predictions aligned with the normal precipitation trend tend to be more accurate. The zero precipitation and high precipitation scenarios result

in slightly higher errors, which is expected given their role in simulating sudden and extreme weather conditions changes. This behaviour can be observed in lakes such as Plötzensee (ID 5800312) and Großglienicker See (ID 5800305), where all three scenarios produce low error values, suggesting a more stable behaviour. In contrast, lakes like Fennsee (ID 5800313) or Flughafensee (ID 5800303) present significantly higher error metrics, reflecting more complex dynamics or greater variability in the historical data, which is a greater challenge for accurate forecasting.

Lake ID	Lake Name	MAE High	MAE High	MAE Forecast	MSE Forecast	MAE Zero	MSE Zero
5800314	Weißer See	2.251	11.118	1.022	3.365	1.025	3.478
5800308	Hundekehlesee	3.033	25.234	2.495	21.073	2.537	21.962
5800313	Fennsee	7.048	107.670	5.456	79.450	5.299	76.732
5800310	Waldsee Zehlendorf	4.642	48.962	2.895	22.694	3.024	25.875
5800305	Großglienicker See	1.271	3.078	0.845	1.651	0.900	1.888
5800317	Biesdorfer Baggersee	3.983	41.415	2.811	27.725	2.804	27.624
5800315	Obersee	3.724	26.059	2.095	11.799	2.249	14.191
5800301	Dianasee	4.096	48.455	3.271	37.955	3.414	40.572
5800320	Fennpfuhl	2.944	18.748	2.087	13.959	2.052	14.264
5800318	Malchower See	3.553	25.852	1.750	12.478	1.957	14.457
5800106	Schäfersee	3.189	24.218	2.783	21.272	2.776	21.597
5800309	Lietzensee	1.315	3.521	0.959	2.389	1.023	2.658
5800316	Orankesee	2.903	16.321	2.536	15.983	2.532	17.140
5800306	Halensee	5.199	59.467	3.139	31.063	3.463	35.416
5800303	Flughafensee	5.966	77.332	3.295	38.220	3.255	40.287
5800312	Plötzensee	1.622	4.863	0.768	1.645	0.867	2.046

Table 2.1: MAE and MSE for water level predictions across all lakes, under three precipitation scenarios.

In the following pages, some visuals are going to be provided for further assessing the obtained results. To ease the readability of the document, the most illustrative examples were selected and reported here. Nonetheless, Annex A: Full-horizon predictions for all lakes includes additional visualizations for all lakes, covering the complete prediction span. These extended plots allow for a more thorough evaluation of the model's ability to capture long-term trends and react to abrupt changes in water levels. Given the large volume of graphics, they are provided in the annex for readability.

Figure 2.4 provides a visual example of the model's short-term prediction output for the lake Flughafensee (5800303). It compares the actual water level with the model's predictions over the final 7 days of the dataset under the three already defined precipitation scenarios: forecast, zero precipitation, and high precipitation. Notably, the forecast-based prediction (orange line) closely follows the real reported data (blue line), while the zero (green) and high (red) precipitation scenarios show slight deviations. This is consistent with the

behaviour observed in Table 2.1. Ideally, the forecast line should align closely with the real water level, and the actual values should fall within the range delimited by the zero and high precipitation predictions. In this example, the model performs as expected, with the real values properly enclosed between the two boundary scenarios.

Figure 2.4: Predicted water levels for Lake 5800303 over the last 7 days of data under three precipitation scenarios.

Figure 2.5 illustrates a contrasting example, showing the prediction results for the lake Orankesee (ID 5800316) over the last 7-day period. In this case, the forecasted water levels are close to the zero-precipitation scenario, although the actual reported levels rather follow the high precipitation scenario. During May 23rd and May 26th, the reported water levels exceed both the forecast and high precipitation predictions, indicating sudden rises. After these days, the water level returns to lie between the high and low precipitation scenarios prediction, suggesting that precipitation decreased, and conditions stabilized.

Figure 2.5: Predicted water levels for Lake 5800316 over the last 7 days of data under three precipitation scenarios.

To provide a more comprehensive assessment of the model’s behaviour across the full validation period, Figure 2.6 compares the reported water level with the forecasted values for lake Orankesee (ID 5800316). The model performs 7-day forecasts repeatedly using a rolling window approach, for each prediction step, the previous 180 days of observed data are used as input. Then, the input window is advanced by 7 days, and the forecasting process is repeated.

The model is able to capture the overall trend and respond to significant fluctuations in water levels. Although in some cases the model fails to capture the oscillations presented in the ground-truth, as seen near the start of 2017, it is capable of consistently follow the general tendency overall years. This suggests that the model can understand the variation patterns of this lake's water level, even when rises and falls occur.

Figure 2.6: Predicted water levels for Lake 5800316 covering the entire prediction horizon for a normal precipitation scenario.

As mentioned before, *Annex A: Full-horizon predictions for all lakes* includes a full detail of all the predictions for all lakes. Given the large volume of graphics, they are provided in the annex for readability.

2.2 PILOT 2: BIODIVERSITY

As described in D5.1, pilot 2 is built around the idea of using AI/ML models for biodiversity conservation and ecological connectivity, which are increasingly recognized as critical global and European policy priorities. Functional Landscape Connectivity (FLC) is a metric that measures the ability of species to move through landscapes, and thus it is a key factor in maintaining biodiversity. In this sense, pilot 2 focuses on the Catalonia region in Spain as a case study, exploring the different approaches to quantifying connectivity, such as graph-based models and remote sensing methods, to provide a better understanding of FLC and guide decision-making organisms related to protected areas, land use planning, and agricultural practices.

In the context of WP5, the idea was to research an AI-based alternative to translate Land Use Land Cover (LULC) maps into connectivity maps (represented by the terrestrial connectivity index or ICT for its meaning in Spanish – *Índice de Conectividad Terrestre*) for areas such as forests, shrublands, herbaceous crops, and woody crops. These connectivity maps are vital for biodiversity conservation, as they help to inform land use planning, agricultural practices, and decisions related to protected areas. Up until now, the process of translating LULC maps into ICT values is computationally expensive because it needs nested iterations, since for each pixel in the LULC map, a calculation has to be done in its neighbourhood to compute the ICT value. The idea, hence, is to use AI to replace this exact calculation by the approximation provided by the inference of an AI model to try to achieve satisfactory results in a considerably lower amount of time. The impact of having this kind of analysis is crucial for actions such as evaluating the implications of introducing a modification in the landscape (e.g., building a highway dissecting a forest habitat). In that situation, many different possible scenarios would have to be evaluated, and the time consumed to evaluate all of them may make this feasibility study not viable.

In the following subsections, the process of developing the model will be detailed, including the deployment and validation stage. In the validation part, an analysis of execution times will be also provided.

2.2.1 MODEL DEVELOPMENT, DEPLOYMENT AND VALIDATION

Similarly to what was presented for pilot 1, in the present section the process of developing the model for pilot 2 is going to be detailed. To ease understanding, a summary of D5.1 is provided, and some images are reused.

Considering the complexity of the input and output data, in this case the development focused not only on the model development itself, but also on the pre-processing and post-processing stages needed for the AI model to work and for the end-users to have the resulting ICT maps. For that reason, this section is divided in three subsections: pre-processing, model development and post-processing.

2.2.1.1 PRE-PROCESSING

As just mentioned, one of the objectives of pilot 2 is to research upon the possibility of substituting the exact, computationally complex computation of ICT maps by an AI-based tool. As already explained in previous deliverables, this complex computation to generate ICT maps is currently done by the MiraMon software, following the algorithm described in [14], in which connectivity is calculated per pixel based on the land use class of that pixel and their surrounding ones at a maximum radius of 2.5 km and some friction values among classes. This results in a ICT values ranging from 0 to 2.5 (from lower to highest connectivity). As ICT calculation is based on land use classes, a proper LULC map is needed. In this case, the Catalan MUCSC (Map of Uses and Covers of Catalonia) was used, and which is delivered in periods of 5 years starting from 1987 (using image classification of only Landsat series) to 2022 (combining Landsat and Sentinel series). All these LULC maps present a spatial resolution of 30m. Due to the high processing time for this calculation at 30 m for the whole Catalonia, these indices were deployed at 390 m resolution for every year and every class, and only 2 periods are available at 30 m (1987 and 2022). An example of this kind of map can be found in Figure 2.7, where each pixel is associated with one of 8 classes:

- 0 = No data
- 1 = Aquatic environment
- 2 = Urban
- 3 = Herbaceous crops
- 4 = Woody crops
- 5 = Shrublands
- 6 = Forest
- 7 = Bare soil

Out of these 8 classes, 5 of them are of interest: aquatic environment, herbaceous crops, woody crops, shrublands and forest. As will be seen later in the document, ICT maps are generated per class, so consequently, one ML model will be needed for each class, resulting in a total of 5 models developed.

As mentioned, regarding the size of the LULC maps, two variations of the input dataset were used for ML model development:

- High-resolution LULC maps: 8651x8981 pixels, resulting in a 30 m spatial resolution
- Low-resolution LULC maps: 655x690 pixels, resulting in a 390 m spatial resolution.

This difference in the resolution of the input dataset has a direct impact in the ML model architecture. As will be seen in Section 2.2.1.2, the ML models used to process images perform some operations (mainly, convolutions and deconvolutions) that have the objective of reducing and increasing the image size. Consequently, the size of the input image has a direct impact in the number of operations that must be performed. Hence, two variations of the ML models were built, one for the high-resolution images, and

another for the low-resolution ones, as will be detailed later in the document. Considering that it was already established that 5 different models have to be produced, this means a total of 10 models have to be trained.

As described before, regarding the output, the images generated are ICT output maps. In the specific case of pilot 2, the maps take a value in the range [0, 2.5]. For illustrative purposes, an example of an ICT map is provided in Figure 2.8.

Figure 2.7: LULC example for Catalonia area corresponding to 1987 (extracted from D5.1).

Figure 2.8: Calculated ICT_Forest for Catalonia area corresponding to 1987 (extracted from D5.1). Please note that light colors represent low connectivity. In most of the other maps presented in this deliverable the coloring criteria is the opposite.

As a last remark, regarding input and outputs, an important issue that was already covered in D5.1 was the need for tiling both inputs and outputs in order to get a more manageable ML model, as observed in Figure 2.9. This process was automated and integrated in the pipeline developed for pilot 2, as will be described in Section 2.2.2. Specifically, the input images (in .tiff format) are divided in tiles of 256x256 for the high-resolution images, and in tiles of 32x32 for the low-resolution ones.

Figure 2.9: Input (left) and output (right) maps tiled into smaller images that are easier to handle using a ML model (extracted from D5.1).

2.2.1.2 MODEL DEVELOPMENT

Regarding model development, the task of mapping LULC data to connectivity maps falls under the domain of image-to-image translation, which is different from the time series forecasting problem discussed in pilot 1, as it involves spatial data. Similarly to the approach followed for pilot 1, in the remaining of the section a brief description of each of the considered models is going to be provided. Then, the final architecture for the model chosen will be detailed.

The following models were considered for the task at hand:

- **Fully Convolutional Networks (FCNs) [9]:** This model was selected because it is one of the most traditional models used for segmentation tasks. It is known for its ability to capture spatial features at different scales and is often used in tasks such as semantic segmentation. FCNs are designed to work well with structured image data, and they can produce segmentation maps directly from pixel-level information. However, while they perform well in segmentation, they lack the capability to generate high-quality, visually realistic images. The LULC to connectivity map translation required in pilot 2 demands not just accurate spatial relationships between pixels, but also coherence and sharpness in the output maps. FCNs operate in a pixel-wise regression manner, which can result in blurry and less detailed images when the spatial patterns in the data are complex, such as the detailed ecological linkages in connectivity maps. Additionally, FCNs fail to incorporate contextual information about landscape structures, which is critical in determining how various land cover types interact ecologically. Ultimately, this made FCNs a less ideal candidate for the task at hand, where the relationships between land cover types and their spatial connectivity are essential.
- **U-Net [10]:** This model is also widely used for segmentation and image translation tasks. It consists of an encoder-decoder architecture, where the encoder captures hierarchical features from the input

image, and the decoder reconstructs the output. This model has proven successful in medical image segmentation and other domains where pixel-wise predictions are required. However, while U-Net can generate reasonably accurate outputs, it often struggles with producing high-quality and coherent images, especially when the output requires capturing fine-grained details. This is particularly evident when generating connectivity maps, which demand visual realism and ecological accuracy.

- **Pix2Pix [11]:** The Pix2Pix model, based on Conditional Generative Adversarial Networks (cGANs), excels in tasks where the goal is to generate high-quality, realistic images conditioned on an input image. In this case, the model is conditioned on LULC maps to generate connectivity maps. Pix2Pix works by utilizing two main components: the generator and the discriminator [12]. The generator creates the connectivity map from the LULC map, while the discriminator evaluates whether the generated map is realistic enough to be classified as "real" or "fake." Through adversarial training, where the generator learns to deceive the discriminator into thinking its generated maps are real, the generator improves over time, becoming better at producing high-quality outputs. This approach is particularly beneficial when the spatial relationships and fine details in the connectivity map are crucial, as it ensures the generated map captures complex ecological patterns.

To sum up, the decision of choosing Pix2Pix over FCN and U-Net, was based on the following:

- First, it enhances the sharpness and coherence of the generated connectivity maps, which is critical for accurately visualizing ecological connections.
- Second, it captures more effectively the spatial dependencies between different land cover types.
- Finally, the model's ability to adapt to various input scenarios makes it more robust in handling different types of LULC maps and generating realistic output under varying ecological conditions.

In D5.1, the selection of the Pix2Pix model architecture was already presented, but the work reported in that moment was still in the early phases of development and thus, no further descriptions were provided about the model architecture, as it was expected to evolve. In the following, a comprehensive description of the final models is provided. It should be noted that, as described in Section 2.2.1.1, due to the different resolution of the LULC maps, two Pix2Pix models were trained for each of the scenarios (forest, herbaceous crops, woody crops, shrublands, and aquatic environment): one for high resolution images, and another for low resolution images. To simplify this section, in the following the model architecture described is going to be the high resolution one, since for the low resolution, the architecture is analogous, as will be seen later.

As mentioned before, Pix2Pix models contain two components:

- **Generator:** The generator follows the U-Net architecture described above. This architecture consists of an encoder-decoder structure, with skip connections between corresponding layers of the encoder and decoder to preserve fine details. The primary goal of the generator is to take an input LULC map and transform it into a connectivity map (such as forest connectivity or shrubland connectivity), capturing complex features of the land cover.
 - o **Encoder block:** The encoder of the generator is built using a series of convolutional layers that progressively reduce the spatial resolution of the input image while increasing the depth of the feature maps. These layers are designed to capture high-level features from the input image. The architecture consists of 8 consecutive Conv2D layers, which are two-dimensional convolutional layers commonly used in image processing. Each layer applies a 4×4 convolution, meaning it scans the input using a small 4×4 grid to detect patterns. These layers use the ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) activation function, which introduces non-linearity by setting all negative values to zero, helping the model learn complex patterns. A stride of 2 is used, which means the convolutional filter moves 2 pixels at a time across the image, effectively reducing the spatial dimensions (height and width) of the feature maps. The number of filters (i.e., the set of pattern detectors in each layer) increases with depth, starting from 64 and going up to 512 in the later layers. This allows the model

to capture more abstract and detailed features as the image resolution decreases. Additionally, L2 regularization is applied to these layers, which helps prevent overfitting (when the model memorizes training data instead of generalizing) by adding a penalty to the loss function based on the size of the layer weights, discouraging overly complex models. The use of ReLU activation introduces non-linearity, allowing the network to learn complex patterns in the data. The first 4 layers progressively reduce the image dimensions while capturing low-level features, such as edges, textures, and shapes. The remaining 4 layers continue this process, but with more abstract, high-level feature extraction, helping the model recognize broader structures in the image, like larger regions of connectivity.

- **Decoder block:** The decoder is designed to reverse the downsampling process by upsampling the feature maps back to the original image size. It uses transposed convolutional layers, allowing the network to retain spatial information that might have been lost during the downsampling process. The architecture consists of 8 consecutive Conv2DTranspose layers, which use 4x4 convolutions with a stride of 2 to upsample the feature maps. Similar to the encoder, these layers use ReLU activation and L2 regularization. Each layer progressively increases the spatial resolution of the feature maps, starting from the deepest features and working towards the original resolution of the image. The skip connections from the encoder are concatenated with the output of these layers, helping the model combine high-level features from the deeper layers with fine-grained details from the earlier layers of the encoder. This helps preserve fine details in the generated output. The first few layers (1-4) increase the spatial resolution of the feature maps, helping reconstruct the connectivity map's structure. The following layers (5-8) refine these features to restore the image to its original 256x256 size. Within them, the final layer in the generator (8) is a transposed convolutional layer that maps the upsampled feature maps to a single-channel output, representing the connectivity map for a specific land cover class (e.g., forest, herbaceous crops). A sigmoid activation is applied to this layer, ensuring that the output is in the range [0, 1], which is suitable for image-to-image translation tasks like this one. The sigmoid activation makes the output compatible with the expected pixel values of a connectivity map.
- **Discriminator:** The discriminator is designed to be a binary classifier, determining whether an image is real (i.e., a true connectivity map) or fake (generated by the generator). The discriminator takes a pair of images as input: the input LULC map and the target connectivity map (either real or generated) and uses this paired data to distinguish between real and fake outputs. The architecture of the discriminator consists of a series of convolutional layers that extract features from the concatenated input-output pair:
 - **Initial convolutional layers:** The discriminator begins with a concatenated input of size 256x256 pixels, where the input LULC map and the corresponding target connectivity map are stacked together. This allows the model to learn the relationship between the two images and evaluate the validity of the generated outputs. The first few layers perform downsampling using convolutions, progressively reducing the spatial resolution while increasing the number of feature maps. The first 4 layers of the discriminator are 2D convolutional layers with LeakyReLU activation. These layers use 4x4 kernels with a stride of 2, effectively downsampling the image while capturing features. The first layer in this block reduces the spatial size of the input while capturing the basic features, while the other 3 further extract more abstract features, helping the discriminator identify the differences between real and generated images.
 - **Deep convolutional layer:** After the initial convolutional layers, the discriminator applies additional convolutions and padding to further refine the extracted features. Here, a conv layer with 512 filters and a 1x1 kernel is used with stride 1. This layer captures more global

features from the input, which are crucial for distinguishing real and fake images in the later stages of the network.

- Final convolutional layer: The final layer of the discriminator is another 1x1 convolution that outputs a single scalar value. This value represents the probability that the input image pair (input LULC map and target connectivity map) is real (as opposed to generated). A sigmoid activation is applied to this layer, which outputs a probability between 0 and 1.

The model architecture for high resolution images (256x256 pixels) is visually represented in Figure 2.10, while the architecture for low resolution images (32x32 pixels) is presented in Figure 2.11. As can be observed, the architecture for low resolution images is essentially the same, but with less layers to adapt to smaller images.

Figure 2.10. Detail of the architecture of the final Pix2Pix model developed for pilot 2 for high resolution input images

Figure 2.11. Detail of the architecture of the final Pix2Pix model developed for pilot 2 for low resolution input images

As will be seen in Section 2.2.3, after training, the model will be evaluated using MAE and MSE, which help to assess the accuracy of the generated connectivity maps by comparing them with the ground-truth images. Additionally, the predicted connectivity maps will be visually compared to the ground-truth ones to assess their quality.

2.2.1.3 POST-PROCESSING

In the post-processing phase of Pilot 2, once the models are trained, the output tiles must be sewn back together to reconstruct the full image. This process is crucial for handling large images that were split into smaller tiles for computational efficiency during the model's inference phase.

The main steps of the image reconstruction process are as follows: starting from the predicted tiles, which have to be combined to generate the new image, **a Hanning window is first applied** to each tile [13]. The Hanning window is used in the image reconstruction process to reduce edge artefacts and smooth transitions between tiles, improving the final image quality. By attenuating values at the edges of each tile, it minimizes harsh visual seams and ensures a natural blending of overlapping regions. This smoothing effect helps preserve fine details and coherence in the reconstructed image, which is crucial for tasks like connectivity mapping. It allows for more accurate and visually consistent outputs by efficiently handling overlaps and ensuring a seamless integration of tile data, hence enhancing the precision of ecological and spatial analysis. Then, to ensure smooth transitions between adjacent tiles, **the weighted pixel values are summed in the overlapping regions and divided by a weight map**. This ensures that the overlapping areas are averaged correctly, preventing any discontinuities or visible seams in the reconstructed image.

The reconstructed image maintains the original spatial dimensions of the input image, ensuring that the output is coherent and consistent with the initial data, while also reducing artefacts introduced during tiling. This post-processing step is essential to generate high-quality, seamless connectivity maps from the predicted tiles, ensuring that the final output is visually accurate and suitable for further analysis or decision-making processes.

2.2.2 AI MODEL PIPELINE

As reported in D5.1, Pilot 2 implementation in WP5 provides an AI prediction model pipeline that works “on demand”. As happened with pilot 1, the pilot 2 model was also trained following the ML lifecycle represented in Figure 2.2. The process of deploying the model in production is also similar to that of pilot 1, the only difference being that this model is exposed through an Application Programming Interface (API) to be called every time a new iteration is required by the end user.

Hence, the AI prediction pipeline for pilot 2 works as follows:

- First, the incoming raw data is stored in MinIO, creating a large historical dataset used to develop, train and test the pilot’s models.
- As just mentioned, the model is exposed through a Representational State Transfer (REST) web API to be called by the end-user in an “on-demand” fashion.
- To perform these API calls, the end user needs to provide an input image. When this is performed, the first action is to preprocess the input image to tile it as described in Section 2.2.1.1.
- When the model finishes the inference, the post-processing step described in Section 2.2.1.3 is executed, providing an output image with the results to the frontend of the system, which formats and presents the result to the end-user. The frontend implementation will be detailed in Section 3.2.

This pipeline was proposed in D5.1, and at the time of writing this deliverable, the system is in place. The process of providing an input to the API and getting the predicted result is represented in Figure 2.12.

Figure 2.12: Pilot 2 “on demand” ML Model’s inferencing schema.

2.2.3 RESULTS

In D5.1, for pilot 2 the work focused on selecting the most suitable model for the problem at hand, and some preliminary results were presented for the ICT for the Forest class. Since then, all the remaining models were trained and evaluated. In this section, a thorough analysis of them is provided.

To perform this evaluation, as mentioned before, metrics such as MAE and MSE were used, and additionally the predicted connectivity maps were visually compared to the ground-truth ones to assess their quality.

The ground-truth images, as described in D5.1, were computed with the MiraMon software [15]. As mentioned at the beginning of Section 2.2, one of the main goals pursued by this pilot is to study the viability

of substituting the MiraMon ICT algorithm with an AI-based solution, as long as this solution is able to provide satisfactory results in a timeframe much more limited than that taken by the software. As a result, this section will not only focus on assessing the results from a functional point of view, but also timing measurements will be provided in order to address the full comparison among the two methodologies.

Before getting into the details of the accuracy of the models, first a thorough analysis of the input data available is needed. Section 2.2.1.1 described in detail LULC images, which are the input images to the Pix2pix model. Specifically, Figure 2.7 contained an example of these images. The mentioned section also discussed the pre-processing stage, which involved tiling the image as presented in Figure 2.9, which is what the model is expecting as the input data.

Meanwhile, Figure 2.8 provided an example of the model's output for the ICT for the Forest class. Table 2.2 describes the volume of ground-truth images available for each class, which represent the model's expected output required for training and validation. For the high-resolution dataset, there is only one input image per class, except for the Forest class, which includes two images. In contrast, the low-resolution dataset contains eight images for each class.

The rationale behind this limited data availability was already discussed in Section 2.2.1.1: the ground-truth images were generated with the MiraMon software, which applies the complete algorithm pixel by pixel in a very high computer consuming time. Due to this computing time, the ground-truth images at 30 m (high-resolution) were only calculated for the 2 extreme periods: 1987 and 2022. This fact has led to have very few images for training the ML models at this very high resolution but also leads to the impossibility to compare the results with the ground-truth for the years in which the ICT hasn't been calculated.

This is the reason why, for the Forest class, two images are available for high-resolution (in 1987 and 2022), while for low-resolution, one image per period is provided (1987, 1992, 1997, 2002, 2007, 2012, 2017 and 2022). In all these cases, the differences between the output and the truth were calculated.

The limited data availability also reinforces the need for the tiling process described in Section 2.2.1.1, allowing each image to be divided into smaller patches, increasing the effective dataset size for both model training and evaluation. Table 2.2 also includes the number of tiles obtained per class, of which 80% were used for training and 20% for evaluation.

Class	Resolution	Images	Tiled Images
Forest	High	2	2310
	Low	8	3360
Aquatic	High	1	1122
	Low	8	3360
Herbaceous crops	High	1	1119
	Low	8	3360
Shrublands	High	1	1121
	Low	8	3360
Woody crops	High	1	1121
	Low	8	3360

Table 2.2: Summary of the ground truth available data for each class and resolution level.

Given that a single image is insufficient to train and evaluate a model capable of generalisation, a first proof of concept was developed for the Forest class, aiming to demonstrate the feasibility of the pipeline and to enable predictions of high-resolution connectivity maps. Regarding the high-resolution models for Aquatic,

Herbaceous crops, Shrublands, and Woody crops connectivity indexes, the model development efforts concluded that no model produced stable or generalizable results when trained on only one image, so it was decided to not continue the implementation efforts. Nonetheless, it should be noted that, as will be seen below, the Forest class can be used as an example of the potential of these models: extending the methodology, pipeline and solution proposed for the ICT for the forest class to the other classes is a straightforward process, as long as more images are included in the training dataset.

Table 2.3 presents the performance results of the implemented models, including the low-resolution models for all classes and the high-resolution model for Forest. For each class, the MAE and MSE are computed by comparing the model's predictions against the corresponding ground-truth values. As described before, the ground-truth used for this study are the images produced by the MiraMon algorithm.

To gain a detailed understanding of the implemented models' behaviour, the evaluation is stratified into three distinct value ranges, defined according to the ground-truth values. The target variable represents a connectivity index on a continuous scale from 0 to 2.5, divided into three equal-width intervals:

- Low (0–0.83): Regions with low connectivity.
- Mid (0.83–1.66): Regions with moderate connectivity.
- High (1.66–2.5): Regions with high connectivity.

The pixel selection for each interval is based on the ground-truth values. For each pixel falling within a given range, the corresponding predicted value is retrieved and compared to the ground-truth. This approach enables a more accurate assessment of the model's predictive performance across different levels of connectivity, helping to identify whether the model performs consistently or struggles in specific regimes. The table also reports the global MAE and MSE calculated over all pixels, providing an overall measure of model accuracy.

These results show notable differences in prediction accuracy across both classes and value ranges. The Aquatic class achieves the lowest global error in the low-resolution setting, indicating that the model learns and generalizes well for these land cover types. It achieves an excellent performance with a global MAE of 0.102 and MSE of 0.041. Although it exhibits higher error in the high value range, this can be attributed to the lack of high-value samples in the dataset, a limitation discussed further in Table 2.4.

The models for Forest and Herbaceous Crops classes display more balanced behaviour, with relatively similar error rates across the three ranges and moderate global error. These results suggest that despite possible spatial fragmentation, the models are capable of capturing recurring patterns and generalizing adequately under certain conditions, as reflected in the global metrics.

The Woody Crops class model presents a low global error. However, when analysing performance by value range, the low and high intervals show some of the highest errors among all classes. This suggests that the model tends to concentrate predictions around the middle range, struggling to learn the characteristics of extreme values.

In contrast, the Shrublands model shows considerably higher errors when analysed by range. While it may correctly identify key corridor areas between habitats, it fails to generalize well in regions where such corridors are absent or minimal.

For the high-resolution Forest model, the results are noticeably better compared to all the low-resolution models. Although only two high-resolution images were available for training, the significantly higher number of pixels enabled the model to generalize effectively. This serves as a promising indication that the methodology can be extended to other high-resolution classes, provided that additional training data is made available.

Classes	Range	MAE	MSE
Forest (high-resolution)	low (0–0.83)	0.146755	0.119444

	mid (0.83–1.66)	0.174027	0.09855
	high (1.66–2.5)	0.108225	0.024033
	Global	0.136178	0.063701
Forest (low- resolution)	low (0–0.83)	0.344773	0.289653
	mid (0.83–1.66)	0.290891	0.153374
	high (1.66–2.5)	0.326025	0.191686
	Global	0.31734	0.194287
Aquatic	low (0–0.83)	0.085501	0.02279
	mid (0.83–1.66)	0.38759	0.248477
	high (1.66–2.5)	1.504391	2.428723
	Global	0.101884	0.041202
Herbaceous crops	low (0–0.83)	0.540481	0.457338
	mid (0.83–1.66)	0.244284	0.110682
	high (1.66–2.5)	0.31132	0.194976
	Global	0.337853	0.221753
Shrublands	low (0–0.83)	1.235395	1.816124
	mid (0.83–1.66)	0.329548	0.181813
	high (1.66–2.5)	0.323397	0.185246
	Global	0.357595	0.240024
Woody crops	low (0–0.83)	0.615762	0.550442
	mid (0.83–1.66)	0.192254	0.085152
	high (1.66–2.5)	0.612103	0.487093
	Global	0.285424	0.178052

Table 2.3: Performance of the models across the five land cover classes. Includes both low-resolution results for all classes, as well as high-resolution results for Forest index.

Overall, the stratified evaluation reveals that model performance varies significantly across the connectivity spectrum, largely due to class imbalance and the spatial distribution of values. To support this interpretation, Table 2.4 summarizes several indicators of complexity in the ground-truth data. The first three columns report the percentage distribution of pixels in each of the three defined connectivity ranges: low (0–0.83), mid (0.83–1.66), and high (1.66–2.5). The fourth column, entropy, quantifies the diversity of pixel values using Shannon entropy: higher values indicate more evenly distributed values across the range, while lower values indicate concentration in specific intervals. The final column, pixel-wise, represents the

average standard deviation across pixel intensities, where higher values suggest more local variation and less spatial smoothness, which generally make the learning task harder for models.

Class	Low (%)	Mid (%)	High (%)	Entropy	Pixel-wise
Aquatic	98.36	1.43	0.21	1.42	0.0090
Forest	61.18	16.88	21.94	2.04	0.0341
Herbaceous crops	64.41	23.06	12.53	2.02	0.0342
Shrublands	55.18	20.82	24.00	1.90	0.0351
Woody Crops	56.19	35.18	8.63	1.69	0.0258

Table 2.4: Distribution of ground-truth connectivity values, entropy and distribution for each land cover class.

The Aquatic class is a clear outlier, with 98.36% of its pixels falling into the low connectivity range and minimal representation in the mid and high ranges. This is clearly visible in Figure 2.13, where the entire region is coloured in dark tones, corresponding to near-zero connectivity values. The class also exhibits the lowest entropy (1.42) and pixel-wise standard deviation (0.009), confirming that the image is both visually and statistically homogeneous. This high degree of uniformity explains the strong performance of the Aquatic model in the low and mid ranges, as well as the low performance in the high range observed in Table 2.3, which can be attributed to the near absence of training samples in that value range.

The other classes present similar entropy and pixel-wise values, with between 55% and 65% of their pixels located in the low connectivity range. Both the Aquatic and Woody Crops classes show the lowest proportion of pixels in the high range, which helps explain why these models exhibit the highest errors in the high connectivity range reported for these models in Table 2.3.

The highest errors in the mid-range occur in the low-resolution Forest, Aquatic, and Shrublands models, classes that also have the lowest proportion of mid-range pixels, indicating that the lack of training samples in the mid-range reduces the model's ability to generalize in that interval.

Similarly, for the low range, the Shrublands and Woody Crops models present the highest error rates, which aligns with their relatively lower representation in that range compared to the other classes.

Finally, the Forest and Herbaceous Crops classes exhibit nearly identical entropy and pixel-wise variability, which corresponds to the similar performance observed for their respective models.

Examples of the expected results for the five models are shown in Figure 2.13, where the pixel distribution patterns for each class, previously described in Table 2.4, are clearly visible. Figure 2.14 presents the corresponding predicted outputs for each of the five land cover classes. Among them, the results for Aquatic, Forest, and Herbaceous Crops are the most promising. In the case of Shrublands and Woody Crops, the overall spatial distribution of the ground truth is reflected in the predictions, but the connectivity patterns are less clearly defined compared to the other models.

Figure 2.13: Ground-truth connectivity maps for each land cover class in the low-resolution dataset (2022).

Figure 2.14: Final connectivity maps predictions for each land cover class in the low-resolution dataset (2022).

Once the comparison between classes was covered, an analysis between the low- and high-resolution models will be discussed taking the Forest land cover class as the example. In Figure 2.15, the image on the left shows the expected ground-truth connectivity map for the Forest class low resolution images, while the image on the right shows the predicted output generated by the model for the year 2022. The prediction closely resembles the reference image, accurately capturing the overall spatial distribution and connectivity patterns of forested areas in the region.

Figure 2.15: Comparison between the expected ground-truth connectivity map (left) and the predicted output (right) for the low-resolution ICT for the Forest class in 2022.

Likewise, Figure 2.16 presents the predicted connectivity map produced by the high-resolution Forest model for the same year (on the right) compared with the expected results (left image). The output demonstrates the model's ability to produce a spatially coherent connectivity map, despite having been trained with a very limited amount of data.

Figure 2.16: Comparison between the expected ground-truth connectivity map (left) and the predicted output (right) for the high-resolution ICT Forest class in 2022.

To complement this analysis, the differences between low-resolution and high-resolution models can also be described using the Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM). High-resolution forest models produce significantly more similar images (SSIM=0.88-0.89) than low-resolution models (SSIM=0.48-0.49) (see Figure 2.17 for an illustrative example of SSIM). This confirms that spatial patterns of connectivity are not fully captured with generalized ground-truth data at low resolution. For other classes, SSIM was intercorrelated with MAE, MSE, entropy and pixel-wise parameters, demonstrating the highest similarity for aquatic habitats (SSIM=0.7-0.72).

Figure 2.17: Example of ground-truth and predicted connectivity with SSIM values spatial distribution (ICT for the forests class, low-resolution model, 2012)

To conclude this subsection, once the results of the models were assessed from a functional point of view, the last experiment to be reported is the comparison in execution time. As mentioned at the beginning of the section, one of the objectives of this use case is to accelerate the process of generating ICT maps, which was one of the motivations to test an AI-based solution instead of using the deterministic MiraMon ICT algorithm implementation. However, it should be clarified the comparison presented in Table 2.5 (as a note, for each type of output, an arithmetic mean of the timings measured for the generation of all 8 ground-truth images is provided) should be considered just as an estimation, since the hardware where these measurements were captured are quite diverse. Specifically:

- As already described, the Pix2Pix models implemented for this use case was both trained and deployed using the HPC resources made available to the consortium within AD4GD project. This HPC cluster was described in detail in Section 2.1 of D5.1, but as a summary, it contains the following resources: 140 virtual CPUs, 272 GB RAM, and 2TB HDD storage.
- The MiraMon ICT algorithm implementation was executed on a personal machine, with its main hardware specifications being Intel(R) Core (TM) i5-10500 CPU @3.10 GHz 16.0 GB RAM.

Output	MiraMon software	Pix2Pix inference
Forest (high-res)	333.52 hours	10min 32 seconds
Forest (low-res)	3.03 hours	1 min 25 seconds
Aquatic	2.63 hours	1 min 25 seconds
Herbaceous crops	3.03 hours	1 min 26 seconds
Shrublands	3.03 hours	1 min 25 seconds
Woody crops	2.78 hours	1 min 25 seconds

Table 2.5: Execution performance (timing) for generating ICT maps, comparing the results with the MiraMon ICT algorithm implementation and those provided by the AI models developed in WP5.

As a conclusion, it was demonstrated that substituting the computing-intensive generation of ICT maps with MiraMon implementation with an AI-based solution shows promising results both in terms of execution time and accuracy of the results. Regarding execution time, it was reduced by several orders of magnitude, going from days to minutes. With respect to the accuracy, the results show that, although the

low availability of input images is a limitation, promising results are obtained for some scenarios where the statistical distribution of the data favours the training of the model, namely in the Forest and Aquatic cases, especially where high-resolution images are used. To validate this proof of concept, the full pipeline was deployed using the HPC resources provided by the project, and the process to obtain an ICT map was fully automated. This pipeline can be extended to all the high-resolution models once more data is available.

Apart from collecting more data, some other research avenues open after these experiments. For example, many habitat connectivity indices calculated through Graphab (see Deliverable 6.1, sections 4.6.1 and 6.7) have not been integrated into these models yet, which could provide further relevant insights. Graphab is another prominent, reusable, and flexible tool for assessing habitat connectivity dynamics, though high-resolution calculations can still take hours to complete. The challenges of this integration lie in the preprocessing part of the pipeline, where the tiling occurs. In this case, changes in at least one tile of the underlying LULC image will cause not only the changes in this tile of output habitat connectivity, but also subtle changes in adjacent tiles, depending on the number of tiles and internal Graphab parameters. Since habitat connectivity calculated through Graphab uses graph theory calculations, changes in one image part may transform the graph structure and change connectivity values in other parts due to the reconfiguration of links between graph nodes.

2.3 FUTURE WORK

The work described in the previous sections closes the experimentation related to applying AI for pilots 1 and 2 of AD4GD project. Although the results obtained are satisfactory and aligned with the project objectives, several research avenues are still open in both pilots that could be explored after AD4GD conclusion.

In pilot 1, the LSTM model was selected for its ability to handle non-linear, long-term dependencies in time series data. By utilizing LSTM, the project benefits from a model that can learn from past water levels and precipitation data to make accurate forecasts, thereby aiding in decision-making for water management in Berlin's lakes. However, as mentioned before, a pending experiment is to get a clustered classification of the lakes based on their behaviour considering both historical, current and predicted values. To continue this research line, the process of identifying the variables in the available data that contribute to that output is still a work in progress.

In pilot 2, the Pix2Pix cGAN model was selected for its ability to handle image-to-image translation tasks efficiently and generate high-quality connectivity maps. The model's architecture makes it well-suited for the complex nature of the problem, where the output maps need to be spatially accurate and detailed. However, as was seen in the results section, although the methodology shows promising results (as shown for the Forest connectivity index) all models have to be improved once more data is available, since that was the main reason why some of the models have not performed as well as expected. In any case, the Forest scenario shows that, indeed, an AI-based tool can be a viable alternative to the MiraMon software, since the obtained results are sufficiently good and the timeframe for generating one ICT map was drastically reduced: for low-resolution images, the execution time decreases from around 3 hours to less than 2 minutes, and for high-resolution images, the impact is even bigger, going from around 300 hours (e.g., 12 days) to just around 10 minutes. Additionally, in that specific case, high-resolution images show particularly promising results considering the extremely limited availability of data, proving that, if eventually more input images are available, an AI-based solution is indeed a very promising option for generating the ICT maps.

3 USER INTERFACES

3.1 DESIGN OF USER INTERFACES

As already reported in D5.1, for the design of the user interfaces in AD4GD, we are following the Human-Centred Design (HCD) approach according to ISO 9241-210 (International Organization for Standardization 2019 [6]), complemented by Co-Design methods in order to build meaningful digital solutions for the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS).

As detailed in D1.1 and D1.2, the Human-Centred Design process consists of four steps: (1) understanding and specifying the context of use, (2) specifying the user requirements, (3) producing design solutions, and (4) evaluating the design. This deliverable specifically reports on the third step, producing design solutions, for Pilot 1 (SplashBoard), Pilot 2 (BioConnect), and the General User Interface.

Throughout the design process, an iterative design approach was followed, as shown in Figure 3.1. The process includes two iteration cycles before reaching the design freeze stage. Each iteration cycle involves evaluating the current design solution with relevant stakeholders, updating the user requirements based on their feedback, and implementing new or revised design solutions to the user interface to meet the collected requirements. The following sections provide a detailed explanation of the creation of each version of the prototypes for each tool.

Figure 3.1: HCD design process model for designing solutions (extracted from D5.1).

3.1.1 PILOT 1 - SPLASHBOARD

The design process for the Splashboard tool for Pilot 1 (Figure 3.2) was completed and was previously reported in D5.1. The iterative design phases involved evaluating the low-fidelity prototype (Version 2) by three district office employees in Berlin, who provided critical feedback for refining the design. This input facilitated the development of a high-fidelity prototype (Version 3). Furthermore, the high-fidelity prototype underwent a thorough and continuous review by the pilot partner, leading to minor adjustments based on their insights. Thus, the Splashboard design was finalized as already reported and optimized beyond the Design Freeze stage through continuous feedback.

Figure 3.2: Current state HCD process model for designing solutions - Pilot 1 (extracted from D5.1).

The data displayed in this UI is gathered from the MinIO, FIS-broker and meteo data sources. Not only historical data is displayed, but also AI-enriched data as described in Section 2.1. Furthermore, the data displayed per lake is automatically updated as soon as new data is available respecting the forecasted values for water level.

3.1.2 PILOT 2 - BioCONNECT

The design process for the BioConnect tool for Pilot 2 (Figure 3.3) was completed. Previously the low-fidelity prototype (Version 2) was reported. Since then, interviews with potential end users were conducted in cooperation with the pilot partner CREAM. Appropriate candidates were selected from the existing network of the pilot partner and feedback to the low-fidelity prototype gathered in structured online interviews. This feedback was utilized to develop the high-fidelity prototype (Version 3). Subsequently the pilot lead partner was invited to review the high-fidelity prototype and provide their feedback. Following the review and final adjustments of the prototype according to the pilot feedback, a Design Freeze stage was reached and served as basis for the implementation work.

Figure 3.3: Current state HCD process model for designing solutions - Pilot 2.

This pilot tool can provide a way to interact with the models described previously by creating artificial changes in land usage maps and calculating a variety of connectivity indexes based on either high- or low-resolution machine learning models. The user can create such a “scenario” interactively on a map view. Accordingly, an API call to the ATOS backend triggers the altered connectivity index calculation for the area changed by the user and is returned for side-by-side comparison by the user.

3.1.3 GENERAL USER INTERFACE

As reported previously, there will be no implementation for the AD4GD data space general user interface. Instead, a prototype proposal will be provided as best practice example for a Green Deal Data Space UI. As a result, the evaluation with potential end users was skipped, and the low-fidelity prototype was evaluated and reviewed by the AD4GD project coordinator instead (see Figure 3.4).

Figure 3.4: Current state HCD process model for designing solutions - General User Interface.

The feedback provided by the project coordinator was analysed, and new user requirements were identified. Accordingly, the low-fidelity prototype was updated and a high-fidelity prototype created, utilizing the already established design system (Figure 3.5). The high-fidelity prototype will serve as a best practice example, being presented and review within the AD4GD project consortium.

Figure 3.5: Extract High-Fidelity Prototype (Version 3) - General User Interface (extracted from D5.1).

3.2 FRONT-END IMPLEMENTATION

In Task 5.4 of the front-end implementation, we have selected open.DASH as the primary platform, emphasizing a modular approach where each component is developed as a widget. This design choice enhances the stand-alone functionality of each component while offering flexibility in the user interface and facilitating the cross-usage of developments between pilot applications. The implementation task is now completed for both pilot tools, Splashboard and BioConnect in accordance with the data and tools available through developments in the AD4GD work packages. In the following sections the implementation status achieved for both pilot tools will be described and visualized. An evaluation of the tools and implemented functionality against gathered user requirements (see D1.2) will be conducted for the final evaluation in D6.2.

3.2.1 PILOT 1 - SPLASHBOARD

In D5.1, we reported that Splashboard had already successfully completed the Human-Centred Design (HCD) process and reached the Design Freeze stage. Key features of the implementation included a centralized header widget with navigation tools, an overview button for accessing all water bodies, favourites feature for quick access to preferred lakes, and an information button for insights into the AD4GD project. The landing page (Figure 3.6) integrates a map of Berlin with a comprehensive list of lakes, including a search function for easy location of specific lakes. Furthermore, the user can identify lake trophic state according to the color-coded normalized difference trophic index (NDTrI) on the map and the list of lakes. The respective legend is provided within the map view.

Figure 3.6: Splashboard – Landing page.

Each selected lake has a detail page (Figure 3.7) featuring five primary widgets: a metadata widget displaying general lake information, gauge meters to display the normalized difference trophic index, a timeseries graph widgets for monitoring lake properties over time and water level predictions each with options to download data, and a comments widget for authenticated users to leave feedback on lake details.

Figure 3.7: Splashboard – Lake details page.

The metadata widget features information provided by the pilot lead partner about lake size, area, name, usage, location etc. as well as an interactive map-based view displaying information provided by the Geoportal Berlin as WMS layers integrated through leaflet. The user can switch between layers featuring different annotations using on screen navigations tools and map legend information, which is also pulled from Geoportal Berlin.

The Earth Observation Trophic State and Trophic Trend are both displayed as gauge meters according to ranges and values individual to each lake and provided by the pilot lead partner. These indexes serve as condensed information source for the user about the current health and ecological condition of the water

body as well as the trend of this indicator. There is no interaction between the user and the displayed information.

The lake statistics timeseries graph provides the user access to all data that is collected and harmonized by the project into the respective buckets in the MinIO database. The user can choose the time frame of data that should be displayed as well as the aggregation mode (daily, weekly, monthly or yearly). Depending on the lake, there are different data sets available for different time frames. In general, the user can select any number of data sets representing measurements of “Water Level”, “Water Temperature”, “Air Temperature”, “Precipitation” and “Reference-Evapotranspiration”. The timeseries widget will adjust dynamically and display the appropriate y-axis for the data sets the user selects. In Figure 3.7, the user has selected “Water Level” (black), “Water Temperature” (green) and “Precipitation” (blue).

In connection with what is explained in section 2.1.3, the Lake Prediction timeseries graph widget provides the user access to forecast data provided by AI models for water level in reference to “high”, “no” or “normal” precipitation. This forecast is then displayed alongside the last water level data provided by min.IO. In Figure 3.7, the last measured water level is recorded for the 22nd of June (blue) where the “high precipitation” forecast is displayed beyond 22nd of June (black). The user can select different prediction models simultaneously; the legend will adjust dynamically, whereas the axis remains unchanged due to the same units being displayed. For both timeseries widgets, the user may download the currently displayed graphs as either PNG images or comma-separated values (CSV) files containing the raw data points.

The feedback widget enables registered users to leave comments or notes for example with specific observations they made.

Any lake that is marked by a user as favourite by clicking the respective button in the metadata widget will add that lake to the favourites tab of that user (Figure 3.8). In the favourites tab that can be accessed through the navigation tools, the user is presented with a list of lakes marked as favourites. For each entry in the list, the user is able to interactively access the metadata widget and lake statistics widget from the lake’s details page, as well as access the full lake’s details page through the respective link.

Figure 3.8: Splashboard – Favourites tab.

3.2.2 PILOT 2 - BIOCONNECT

In D5.1, we reported that the BioConnect tool had not completed the Human-Centred Design (HCD) process and reached the Design Freeze stage. Therefore, implementation work for that tool was started later after the Design Freeze was achieved with feedback from interviews with potential end-users and from the

pilot lead partner. Key features of the implementation included a centralized landing page with an interactive map that allows the user to browse layers for land usage, connectivity indexes, species occurrences and infrastructure as well as historical data for the area of Catalonia (Figure 3.9). Additionally, the user can create a scenario where a land usage change is introduced and accordingly connectivity indexes are recalculated utilising computer vision models.

Figure 3.9: BioConnect – Landing page.

In connection with what is explained in section 2.2.3, the scenario creation page (Figure 3.10) presents the user with an interactive map as well as the functionality to draw a polygon shape on this map in order to define an area where the land usage should be changed. Instructions on how to interact with the polygon creation tools are presented to the user in the “How to use” box. Subsequently, the user can assign a land usage to the drawn polygon, e.g. “Forest” in Figure 3.10 (green, value 6). A full list of possible choices is presented to the user in a drop-down menu and its associated map legend: “Aquatic”, “Built area”, “Herbaceous cropland”, “Woody cropland”, “Shrubland and grassland”, “Forest” and “Bare/sparse vegetation”. The user can calculate one connectivity index at a time for the introduced land usage change (polygon). For this either a high- or low-resolution processing mode can be selected alongside the API Parameter Type, which defines the index that will be recalculated for the area: “Aquatic”, “Herbaceous cropland”, “Woody cropland”, “Shrubland and grassland” or “Forest”. Underlying AI models with low resolution are available for all connectivity types, whereas high resolution is only available for the “Forest” class. The selection menu informs the user about incorrect combinations that would fail when calling the API. By clicking “Save Scenario” the user triggers an API call with the defined parameters to the ML backend. The returned calculation results will be presented to the user in a new side-by-side comparison screen.

Figure 3.10: BioConnect – Scenario creation.

The side-by-side comparison screen enables the user to investigate the newly calculated connectivity index for the area of interest in an interactive map on the right side in reference to the initial index on the left side. In Figure 3.11, the user has introduced a land usage change from “Herbaceous cropland” to “Forest” and recalculated the ICT connectivity index for the forest class. Through the interactive map, the user can directly investigate the calculated change in connectivity within the polygon of the land usage change and adjacent pixels. The total area affected by the calculation is marked with a red dotted square to indicate its location. For later reference, the user is also able to download the reference and calculated connectivity index map view as tiff file using the corresponding download icons above the map views.

Figure 3.11: BioConnect – Scenario comparison.

4 SUPPORTING CONVERGENCE OF HPC, CLOUD, DATA AND AI

Task T5.5 “Supporting convergence of high-performance computing, cloud, data and artificial intelligence resources for Earth system modelling” deals with the distribution of the workloads in the different building blocks of the GDDS. Each building block has some advantages compared to the rest and this section explains how to handle the different kinds of data processing activities to be undertaken in the GDDS building blocks.

4.1 LINK WITH OTHER TASKS

Task T5.5 is closely linked to other tasks of the AD4GD project. As one of the main objectives of the project is to make the data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), the Task T2.5 “Ensuring data protection and compliance by design and by default” is relevant to the Task T5.5. Indeed, the different sorts of data collected in the context of the three pilots are shared among different project partners and Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) building blocks or components. So, Task T2.5 brings the necessary and relevant information and tools to be sure that data sharing is fully compliant with the FAIR principles and the current data regulation at the European level. The first important element is the presence of licences for all the datasets created, transformed and shared in the AD4GD project. Task T2.5 also provides legal and organisational solutions to ensure the protection of data, in particular of possible personal or sensitive data. Concerning the Internet of Things (IoT) and the edge, the Task T5.5 is directly associated to the WP3, in particular with Task T3.3 “Scalability and edge computing optimization”. Some data processing activities are executed directly at the edge for the IoT data. This reduces the amount of IoT data to be transferred to the components located in the cloud. Scalability is in consequence improved, with a decrease of the required bandwidth on the Internet network. This point is important in the particular case of IoT sensors installed in remote areas with a limited Internet connection, such as the camera traps or the sensors deployed near certain small lakes. The work realised in Task T3.3 is presented and described in detail in deliverable D3.2 “Scalability and edge computing optimization”.

The other tasks of the WP5, namely Task T5.1 “AI and ML for data quality and uncertainty management and ground-truthing” and Task T5.2 “AI, ML in HPC and cloud for data analytics and knowledge generation”, are of course in relationship with Task T5.5 “Supporting convergence of high-performance computing, cloud, data and artificial intelligence resources for Earth system modelling”.

Finally, Task T6.5 “Scalability, performance, and technology convergence potential assessment”, which started during the second half of the AD4GD project, is evaluating the outcomes of the project. In relation with the results obtained by Task T5.5, some recommendations and actions can be suggested to improve the convergence at the different levels of the future GDDS architecture and scalability.

4.2 DATA FLOW

The initial data flow was described in deliverable D5.1 “AI, ML in HPC and cloud for FAIR Science Services”. Basically, the starting point is the generation of data by the heterogeneous IoT sensors installed at the edge of each AD4GD pilots. Then, the data are transmitted to the cloud for initial data processing involving the Fraunhofer Opensource SensorThings-Server (FROST) / SensorThings API plus (STApplus) server deployed in the IoT Lab research infrastructure. Then, the data are forwarded to the HPC cluster to be processed by the AI/ML modules. Figure 4.1 presents this data flow.

Figure 4.1: Initial data flow from IoT sensors to HPC (extracted from D5.1).

In the second part of the AD4GD project, a new data flow was developed to better fit the needs and the requirements of the ML/AI modules and the objectives of the pilot dedicated to the small lakes in the region of Berlin. This new version is described in Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2: New data flow from IoT sensors to HPC.

In the second version of the data flow, the cloud is now skipped. Indeed, the data generated by the different IoT sensors and other IoT devices are collected as CSV files. The trigger of the data collection is realised by the edge from the IoT Lab research infrastructure: each Monday, the software located at the edge retrieves the weekly data of each kind of IoT sensors and the data are automatically forwarded to the HPC cluster. Then, the data harmonisation tool developed by the PSNC team converts the received CSV files into JSON files compliant with OGC Observations and Measurements (the same semantics used in OGC SensorThings

API). Finally, the AI/ML modules take care of handling the data, in particular to generate the different predictions based on the JSON files. More details can be found in the following sections.

4.2.1 IoT AND EDGE

The first version of the data flow is conserved but the data are not used by the building blocks of the HPC cluster, namely the AI/modules. Indeed, the edge is in charge of collecting the different kinds of data generated by the heterogeneous IoT sensors. The involved data processing uses the IoT communication protocols used by the IoT devices and thus, the edge has also a role as an IoT gateway for the given IoT communication protocol. In the first version of the data flow, the different sorts of IoT data are collected at the maximum frequency available on the IoT sensors; typically, the IoT data are retrieved every hour or even every quarter of an hour. In the second version of the data flow linked to the Internet of Things, the data are retrieved only on a daily basis, as it is sufficient for the AI/ML modules.

As already explained in the deliverable D5.1, the first version of the data flow implies to retrieve the raw data from the sensors, for instance CSV files for the IoT sensors installed on the lakes of the city of Berlin. The parsing and conversion of the original CSV files to JSON files with the OGC Observations and Measurements (the same semantics used in OGC SensorThings API) are executed at the edge. This process is fully aligned with the semantic interoperability outcomes of the AD4GD project, in particular the metadata published on the RAINBOW server. Finally, the IoT data are sent and stored on one of the FROST/STApplus server instances managed by the IoT Lab technical team. The data can be read afterwards using the OGC SensorThings API, and exploited by a current or a new application or service developed in the context of the project.

The second data flow is also collecting the IoT data, but with an hourly frequency. Furthermore, the raw data are not pre-processed but only sent to the HPC cluster. More precisely, the edge is sending the diverse IoT data to the MinIO instance deployed on the HPC cluster using the dedicated API based on the Amazon S3 cloud storage service. In this case, the data harmonization tool developed by PSNC and running on the HPC cluster takes care to convert the CSV files to JSON files by applying several rules concerning the semantic interoperability. Finally, the harmonized data are stored on an instance of a FROST/STApplus server hosted also on the HPC cluster.

4.2.2 HIGH-PERFORMANCE COMPUTING

The main improvement done in the second half of the AD4GD project is to execute the data harmonization directly on the HPC cluster. As mentioned earlier in this document, the second version of the data flow or pipeline permits to retrieve directly the raw data from the edge and then, to forward them to the HPC cluster for further handling.

Furthermore, the HPC cluster configuration was optimized to better handle the data, in particular for the high-demanding AI/ML modules. This allows a high availability not only for the data, but also for the computing resources.

4.3 SECURITY AND PRIVACY

The first iteration of the security measures to ensure a good level of data protection in case of personal or sensitive data consists of using the authentication and the authorization mechanisms available through Authenix for the FROST/STApplus server. Authenix⁵ was specifically designed and developed for European projects dedicated to the citizen science and related research; a large number of European organisations and research centres are using the Authenix authentication and authorization service, so a broad community of users already exists.

During the second half of the AD4GD project, MinIO is extensively used to store the heterogeneous data generated by the three pilots. To ensure the security and the privacy of the different sorts of data collected and stored on MinIO, the access to the MinIO server is limited to authenticated and authorized users and

⁵ <https://www.authenix.eu/>

building blocks. To implement this access, Keycloak⁶ is used to manage the users and their roles. Each partner of the project can access the MinIO server with the individual account defined on Keycloak.

For each building block of the Green Deal Data Space, it is possible to generate an access key and a secret key. Both are required to send data to MinIO through the Amazon S3 API for every request to the MinIO server. This guarantees a good level of cybersecurity and data protection. Finally, as Keycloak is well-established, it allows more potential integration with other building blocks of the GDDS for the topic of security and privacy.

⁶ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

5 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The second half of the project has seen the completion of the developments of WP5, proposing end-to-end prototypes for both pilots and successfully integrating the different blocks developed in WP5.

Starting with the development, deployment and validation of AI/ML models for pilots 1 and 2, this document has validated the models developed for both pilots, obtaining satisfactory results aligned with the project objectives. Although the experiments were considered a success, several research avenues are still open in both pilots that could be explored after AD4GD conclusion.

In pilot 1, the LSTM model was selected for its ability to handle non-linear, long-term dependencies in time series data. By utilizing LSTM, the project benefits from a model that can learn from past water levels and precipitation data to make accurate forecasts, hence assisting in decision-making for water management in Berlin's lakes. Additionally, the model was successfully deployed in a ML pipeline that uses the MLOps platform defined in D5.1 and hosted in the HPC resources of the project. This pipeline represents the integration of all the relevant components, including the data harmonization tool coming from WP1 and the frontend also developed in WP5. Thanks to all these components, predictions for all lakes are being provided on a weekly basis, consuming the new data being captured by the IoT sensors. Regarding future lines, a pending experiment is to get a clustered classification of the lakes based on their behaviour considering both historical, current, and predicted values. To continue this research line, the process of identifying the variables in the available data that contribute to that output is still a work in progress.

In pilot 2, the Pix2Pix cGAN model was selected for its ability to handle image-to-image translation tasks efficiently and generate high-quality connectivity maps. The model's architecture makes it well-suited for the complex nature of the problem, where the output maps need to be spatially accurate and detailed. However, as was seen in the results section, although the methodology shows promising results (as shown for the Forest connectivity index) all models have to be improved once more data is available, since that was the main reason why some of the models have not performed as well as expected. In any case, the Forest class shows that, indeed, an AI-based tool can be a viable alternative to the MiraMon ICT algorithm, since the obtained results are sufficiently good and the timeframe for generating one ICT map was drastically reduced: for low-resolution images, the execution time decreases from around 3 hours to less than 2 minutes, and for high-resolution images, the impact is even bigger, going from around 300 hours (e.g., 12 days) to just around 10 minutes. Additionally, in that specific case, high-resolution images show particularly good results, proving that, if eventually more input images are available, an AI-based solution is indeed a very promising option for generating the ICT map. From an integration point of view, the frontend developed in the context of T5.5 was fully integrated with the API provided in the context of T5.2 to serve the models, thus providing a fully automated service where the end-user can directly input the connectivity map and get the generated ICT map.

These results showcase the successful exploitation of the computing continuum (IoT devices, edge resources, cloud servers and HPC infrastructures) to provide an integrated solution to support some of the priority actions of the European Green Deal, such as biodiversity, climate change, forest-related services, and environmental compliance, which was one of the main objectives in WP5 and in AD4GD. Graphical User Interfaces has been provided for the execution of ML models from web portals.

6 REFERENCES

- [1] Box, G. E. (1970). G. M. Jenkins. Time series analysis: forecasting and control.
- [2] Nelson, B. K. (1998). Time series analysis using autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) models. *Academic emergency medicine*, 5(7), 739-744
- [3] Box, G. E., & Pierce, D. A. (1970). Distribution of residual autocorrelations in autoregressive-integrated moving average time series models. *Journal of the American statistical Association*, 65(332), 1509-1526
- [4] Graves, A. (2012). Long short-term memory. *Supervised sequence labelling with recurrent neural networks*, 37-45.
- [5] Hochreiter, S., & Schmidhuber, J. (1997). Long short-term memory. *Neural computation*, 9(8), 1735-1780.
- [6] Kulathunga, N., Ranasinghe, N. R., Vrinceanu, D., Kinsman, Z., Huang, L., & Wang, Y. (2020). Effects of the nonlinearity in activation functions on the performance of deep learning models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2010.07359*.
- [7] Bai, Y. (2022). RELU-function and derived function review. In *SHS web of conferences* (Vol. 144, p. 02006). EDP Sciences.
- [8] Kingma, D. P., & Ba, J. (2014). Adam: A method for stochastic optimization. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1412.6980*.
- [9] Long, J., Shelhamer, E., & Darrell, T. (2015). Fully convolutional networks for semantic segmentation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* (pp. 3431-3440).
- [10] Ronneberger, O., Fischer, P., & Brox, T. (2015, October). U-net: Convolutional networks for biomedical image segmentation. In *International Conference on Medical image computing and computer-assisted intervention* (pp. 234-241). Cham: Springer international publishing.
- [11] Isola, P., Zhu, J. Y., Zhou, T., & Efros, A. A. (2017). Image-to-image translation with conditional adversarial networks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* (pp. 1125-1134).
- [12] Henry, J., Natalie, T., & Madsen, D. (2021). Pix2pix gan for image-to-image translation. *Research Gate Publication*, 1-5.
- [13] Pielawski, N., & Wählby, C. (2020). Introducing Hann windows for reducing edge-effects in patch-based image segmentation. *PloS one*, 15(3), e0229839.
- [14] Marull Joan, Mallarach Josep M. (2005). A GIS methodology for assessing ecological connectivity: application to the Barcelona Metropolitan Area. *Landscape and Urban Planning*. Volume 71, Issues 2-4. Pages 243-262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2004.03.007>
- [15] Serral, Ivette, et al. "Terrestrial Connectivity Based on Landsat/Sentinel Land Cover Classes as a Biodiversity Indicator for the European Green Deal Data Space." *IGARSS 2024-2024 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*. IEEE, 2024.

7 ANNEX

7.1 ANNEX A: FULL-HORIZON PREDICTIONS FOR ALL LAKES

This annex presents individual plots for each lake analysed in Pilot 1, showing the predicted water levels across the entire validation period under the normal precipitation scenario. These visualizations provide a qualitative complement to the metrics reported in Section 2.1.3. As can be observed, the forecasted values succeed in learning the trends and changes of the historical data, with the exception of some extreme changes in the data.

Figure 7.1: Predicted water levels for Lake 5800306 covering the entire prediction horizon for a normal precipitation scenario.

Figure 7.2: Predicted water levels for Lake 5800301 covering the entire prediction horizon for a normal precipitation scenario.

Figure 7.3: Predicted water levels for Lake 5800303 covering the entire prediction horizon for a normal precipitation scenario.

Figure 7.4: Predicted water levels for Lake 5800305 covering the entire prediction horizon for a normal precipitation scenario.

Figure 7.5: Predicted water levels for Lake 5800306 covering the entire prediction horizon for a normal precipitation scenario.

Figure 7.6: Predicted water levels for Lake 5800308 covering the entire prediction horizon for a normal precipitation scenario.

Figure 7.7: Predicted water levels for Lake 5800309 covering the entire prediction horizon for a normal precipitation scenario.

Figure 7.8: Predicted water levels for Lake 5800310 covering the entire prediction horizon for a normal precipitation scenario.

Figure 7.9: Predicted water levels for Lake 5800312 covering the entire prediction horizon for a normal precipitation scenario.

Figure 7.10: Predicted water levels for Lake 5800313 covering the entire prediction horizon for a normal precipitation scenario.

Figure 7.11: Predicted water levels for Lake 5800314 covering the entire prediction horizon for a normal precipitation scenario.

Figure 7.12: Predicted water levels for Lake 5800315 covering the entire prediction horizon for a normal precipitation scenario.

Figure 7.13: Predicted water levels for Lake 5800316 covering the entire prediction horizon for a normal precipitation scenario.

Figure 7.14: Predicted water levels for Lake 5800317 covering the entire prediction horizon for a normal precipitation scenario.

Figure 7.15: Predicted water levels for Lake 5800318 covering the entire prediction horizon for a normal precipitation scenario.

Figure 7.16: Predicted water levels for Lake 5800320 covering the entire prediction horizon for a normal precipitation scenario.